

2019

Okanagan Fish and Water Management Tool (FWMT) Procedures

Dawn Machin², Kim Hyatt¹, Margot
Stockwell¹, Tara White³, Kari Alex², Lynnea
Wiens², Chelsea Mathieu², Colette Louie⁴

March 2020

Submitted to:
FWMT Steering committee

Okanagan Nation Alliance
101-3535 Old Okanagan Highway,
Westbank, BC V4T 3L7
Phone: (250) 707-0095 Fax: (250) 707-0166

1 Fisheries and Oceans Canada

Science Branch, Pacific Biological Station
3190 Hammond Bay Road
Nanaimo, B. C. V9T 6N7

2 Okanagan Nation Alliance Fisheries Department

101-3535 Old Okanagan Highway,
Westbank, B. C. V4T 3L7

3 British Columbia Ministry of Forests, Lands, Natural Resource Operations & Rural Development

102 Industrial Place
Penticton, B. C. V2A 7C8

4 Osoyoos Indian Band

1165 Sen Pok Chin Blvd,
Oliver, BC V0H 1T0

Disclaimer: This report may contain preliminary data, and conclusions based on these may be subject to change. Reported data was gathered under a data sharing agreement belonging to the three governments. Contact with the authors is recommended in order to align with the data sharing agreement and to clarify any uncertainties associated with interpretation or use of report contents.

Citation: Machin, D., C. Mathieu, L. Weins, T. White, C. Louie, M. Stockwell, K. Hyatt, K. Alex. 2019. Okanagan Fish and Water Management Tool (FWMT) procedures manual. Prepared for the FWMT Steering Committee. Prepared by Okanagan Nation Alliance Fisheries Department, Westbank, BC.

Table of Contents

List of Figures and Tables	iv
List of Acronyms	v
List of Okanagan Names	vi
1.0 Background.....	1
1.1 Monitoring objectives	3
1.2 Monitoring timeline	4
1.3 Study areas.....	4
2.0 Methods	8
2.1 Distribution and abundance of Sockeye.	8
2.1.1 Sockeye abundance estimates	8
2.1.2 Sockeye peak spawning dates	10
2.2 Biological Traits of Adult Sockeye	11
2.2.1 Deadpitch procedures:	11
2.2.2 Biosampling procedures	12
2.3 Distribution and abundance of beach spawning kokanee.....	13
2.4 Biological traits of spawning Kokanee	14
2.5 Sockeye egg hatch and fry emergence timing.....	14
2.6 Fry survival and annual smolt production from Osoyoos Lake.....	16
2.6.1 Temperature / Dissolved Oxygen.....	16
2.6.2 Secchi Depth (day time only)	16
2.6.3 Mysis relicta and zooplankton	17
2.6.4 Acoustic surveys.....	18
2.6.5 Trawl surveys	19
2.6.6 Fish biological sampling from Osoyoos lake	20
3.0 References	21
Appendix A: Sockeye enumeration field data sheet.....	23
Appendix B: Sockeye fry emergence field data sheet.....	27
Appendix C-1: Okanagan Lake Kokanee shore-spawning enumeration.....	29
Appendix C-2: Okanagan Lake Kokanee shore-spawning bio-sampling.....	30
Appendix D-1: Osoyoos Lake sampling schedule	31
Appendix D-2: Temperature, dissolved oxygen, and secchi field data sheet	32
Appendix E-1: Osoyoos Mysid and zooplankton sites.	33
Appendix E-2: Mysid and zooplankton field data sheet and label data sheet.....	34
Appendix F-1: Acoustic transects Osoyoos Lake.	35
Appendix F-2: Acoustic field data sheet.	36
Appendix G: Trawling field data sheet.	37
Appendix H: Photo Documentation.	39

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1 The project is located throughout the Okanagan Valley of B.C's southern interior, a sub-basin on the Columbia River.	2
Figure 2. Map of major lakes, dam sites, monitoring stations and town (adapted from Hyatt et al. 2004).....	5
Figure 3. Okanagan River sockeye spawning grounds. Numbers 1 through 17 are Vertical Drop Structures.	6
Figure 4. General location of four quadrants (NW, NE, SW, SE) used in estimating Okanagan Lake kokanee shorespawners (map image from Andrusak et al. 2013).....	7
Table 1. Monitoring objectives	3
Table 2. Summary of monitoring FWMT objectives	4
Table 3. Sockeye spawner enumeration method	9
Table 4. Sockeye spawner biosampling method.....	11
Table 5. Kokanee beach spawning methods.....	13
Table 6. Sockeye fry emergence methods	14
Table 7. Osoyoos in-lake methods.....	16
Table 8. <i>Mysis relicta</i> and zooplankton sample sites for Osoyoos and Skaha Lake.....	17

List of Acronyms

List of Organizations & Programs

Acronym	Organizations and Programs	Country
COBTWG	Canadian Okanagan Basin Technical Working Group	Canada
DFO	Fisheries and Oceans Canada (federal)	Canada
DCPUD	Douglas County Public Utility district	USA
EC	Environment Canada (federal)	Canada
ESSA	ESSA Technologies Ltd.	Canada
FWMT	Fish-Water Management Tool program	Canada
IJC	International Joint Commission	Can-USA
FLNRORD	B.C. Ministry of Forest, Lands, Natural Resource Operations, and Rural Development	Canada
OIB	Osoyoos Indian Band	Canada
OLRS	Okanagan Lake Regulation System	Canada
ONA	Okanagan Nation Alliance	Canada
ONAFD	Okanagan Nation Alliance Fisheries Department (previously ONFC)	Canada
ORRI	Okanagan River Restoration Initiative	Canada
PIB	Penticton Indian Band	Canada
RFC	River Forecast Centre	Canada
WSC	Water Survey of Canada	Canada

List of Terminology Acronyms

Acronym	Terminology
ASP	Automated Snow Pillow; (Remotely-sensed snow and meteorological data)
ATU	Accumulated Temperature Units
cms	Cubic meters per second also as (m ³ /s)
Kdam³	thousands of cubic decameters = millions of cubic meters
m³/s	Cubic meters per second, also known as m ³ .s ⁻¹
MSP	Manual Snow Pillow; (Manual measurement of snow data)
NA	Not applicable
SWE	or in the case of FWMT, snow water equivalents
TBD	To be determined
TEK	Traditional Ecological Knowledge
VDS	Vertical Drop Structure

List of Okanagan Names

Okanagan Place Names (Okanagan-English Translation)	
aksk ^w ək ^w ant	Inkaneep Creek
nχ ^w əntk ^w itk ^w	Columbia River
n ^f əylintən	McIntyre Dam area
kłusxənitk ^w	Okanagan Lake
q̄awsitk ^w	Okanagan River
q̄awst'ik ^w t, also known as t̄iwçən	Skaha Lake
snɣaχəlqax ^w iya?	Vaseux Creek
suwiŋs	Osoyoos Lake
sχ ^w əχ ^w nik ^w	Okanagan Falls
Okanagan Species Names (Okanagan-English Translation)	
kəkni or kəkni i	Kokanee
ntitiyx or ntytyix	Chinook (spring)
q ^w əyq ^w əyɣaça?	Steelhead
sćwin	Sockeye
x ^w umina?	Rainbow Trout

Translation provided by Richard Armstrong, Penticton Indian Band. Indigenous Peoples of the Okanagan are the exclusive owners of their cultural and intellectual properties.

All field data collection related to this project was implemented according to the directions we received to date from traditional ecological knowledge keepers. This include acknowledgments and respect of the **siwtkw** and **tm'xwula?x**. Indigenous Peoples of the Okanagan are the exclusive owners of their cultural and intellectual properties.

1.0 Background

Annual production variations of both ǰawsitk^w (Okanagan River) sćwin (sockeye salmon) fry and kłusxənitk^w (Okanagan Lake) kəkni (kokanee) are influenced significantly by water regulation decisions. Water is managed at a series of low-head dams built at lake outlets kłusxənitk^w (Okanagan Lake), ǰawst'ik^wt, also known as tíwcən (Skaha Lake), Vaseux, suwiwś (Osoyoos Lake), and in the headwaters of the ǰawsitk^w (Hyatt et al. 2019; Figure 1).

The Fish-and-Water Management Tool (FWMT) Project was initiated in 2001 by COBTWG and funded by the Douglas County Public Utility District, (Hyatt et al. 2001, Hyatt and Machin 2005). The goal was to develop, test, and apply decision-support models to improve water management decisions affecting production variations of Okanagan sockeye and kokanee salmon (*Oncorhynchus nerka*). The FWMT is an online, decision-support tool used by fisheries and water managers to balance competing water resource use, which utilizes six linked biophysical models (water supply – based on inflow forecasts, water management rules, water temperature, kokanee egg-to-fry emergence, Rocky Mountain Ridged Mussel, and Sockeye sub-models) to predict the outcomes of water management scenarios (weekly releases). The FWMT allows an operations team of fish and water managers to “game” in real-time with various water storage or release options and weigh the associated risks and benefits of each prior to key decision points that may be separated by days to weeks. The FWMT predictions and the potential impacts of scenarios are discussed by water and fisheries managers, and decisions regarding water releases are implemented by the regulating agency. Improved communications between fisheries and water managers has led to greater compliance with recommended flows, in particular, fish-friendly lake levels and flows reduce negative impacts to fish populations (Hyatt, et. al. 2015).

The field work of the FWMT need to be based on standardized methods in order to;

1. track in season operation of the annual program,
2. confirm model predictions,
3. record of events/methods that may have changed outcomes, and
4. long term monitoring and evaluation programs required by FWMT to support future synthesis and analyses on biological and hydrologic impacts.

Figure 1 The project is located throughout the Okanagan Valley of B.C.'s southern interior, a sub-basin on the Columbia River.

1.1 Monitoring objectives

The Fish and Water Management Tools (FWMT) program aims to identify local water release practices that reduce the risks that create losses of wild Osoyoos Lake, Okanagan Sockeye and Okanagan Lake kokanee salmon. The primary outcome of this report is to document the field and lab methods used to populate the data needed within FWMT. Objectives of each monitoring task is labeled in Table 1.

Table 1. Monitoring objectives

Performance indicator	Associated ecosystem process monitored and deliverables
Maintenance and monitoring of automated water stations for daily temperature and discharge.	Continuous data stream of unbiased water temperature, discharge, and/or lake level observations that are remotely accessible in real time. Water temperatures are used in the Sockeye and Kokanee sub-model to predict the developmental stage and hence the period of vulnerability of eggs, alevins, and emerging fry to changes in flow rates (<i>i.e.</i> risk of scour and desiccation).
Distribution and abundance of Sockeye.	In-season estimates of abundance and distribution of wild Osoyoos Sockeye on the terminal spawning grounds. Spawn timing is required to initialize FWMT in a given management year.
Biological Traits of Adult Sockeye	Biological traits of Spawned sockeye (deadpitch) to determine sex ratios, age class distribution, and age-size relationships of the spawning population.
Distribution and abundance of beach spawning kokanee.	In-season estimates of abundance and spawn timing of Okanagan Lake beach spawning Kokanee to initialize FWMT spawning timing sub-model in a given management year.
Biological traits of spawning Kokanee	Biological traits of spawned kokanee to determine sex ratios, age class distribution, and age-size relationships of the spawning population.
Sockeye egg hatch and fry emergence timing	In-season estimates of timing of sockeye egg-hatch, fry emergence (<i>i.e.</i> , times to 25%, 50% and 100% hatch and fry emergence) and biological traits of fry (developmental stages, size) as key observations for ongoing verification of FWMT sockeye sub-model predictions.
Sockeye fry survival and annual smolt production from Osoyoos Lake via acoustic and trawl surveys.	Measure juvenile abundance of sockeye attributable to the FWMT project from a given brood year. Results annually are reported out separate from this report.

1.2 Monitoring timeline

A summary of the monitoring timelines used to supply the FWMT with data and monitor success are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of monitoring FWMT objectives

Performance indicator	Monitoring method	Timeline	Details
Maintenance and monitoring of automated water stations for daily temperature and discharge.	Continuous daily mean water temperatures recorded at WSC “real-time” hydrometric monitoring stations 08NM085 (Okanagan River near Oliver) and 08NM083 (Okanagan Lake near Kelowna) and imported into FWMT.	Water year, October 1 to September 30	Analysis of this data for FWMT found in Hyatt et al. 2019
Distribution and abundance of Sockeye.	Completion sockeye-spawner enumeration surveys of the Okanagan River Index, Channel, and above McIntyre Dam sections.	September to November 1	Section 2.3
Biological Traits of Adult Sockeye	Dead-pitch surveys to determine sex ratios, age class distribution, and age-size relationships of the sockeye spawning population.	October to November 15	Section 2.4
Distribution and abundance of beach spawning kokanee.	Field assessments of spawner abundance and peak spawn timing at 3 shore spawning quadrants of Okanagan Lake.	October to November	Section 2.5
Biological traits of spawning Kokanee	Determine sex ratios, age class distribution, and age-size relationships of the kokanee spawning population.	October to November	Section 2.6
Sockeye egg hatch and fry emergence timing	Annual assessments of emerging/migrating fry and sub-sample fry.	March – May	Section 2.7
Fry survival and annual smolt production from Osoyoos Lake via acoustic and trawl surveys.	Measure juvenile abundance of Sockeye attributable to the FWMT project from a given brood year.	All year	Section 2.8 Lab analysis Sec. 2.8.2

1.3 Study areas

The Okanagan River is a regulated river system, with most of the storage (340 Mm³) provided by Okanagan Lake as modified by a dam at the city of Penticton, BC. Minor additional storage is provided in tributary headwater reservoirs (principally for domestic and agricultural use) and in Skaha and Osoyoos Lakes. Map of major lakes, dam sites (Penticton, Okanagan Falls, McIntyre, Zosel), monitoring stations (snow-pack, water supply and temperature) and towns within British Columbia’s Okanagan Basin (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Map of major lakes, dam sites, monitoring stations and town (Hyatt et al. 2017).

The Okanagan sockeye population spawns in October in the Okanagan River between Vaseux and Osoyoos lakes, principally in the 5 km of river immediately downstream of Vaseux Lake. Egg and alevin development to swim-up occur between October and May. Sockeye fry rear in Osoyoos Lake on a year-round basis (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Okanagan River sockeye spawning grounds. Numbers 1 through 17 are Vertical Drop Structures (Hyatt et al. 2017)

The Okanagan FWMT system includes a kokanee sub-model that incorporates the impacts of water storage and release decisions (lake elevation) on egg and alevin survival by simulating the developmental progress of Okanagan Lake shore-spawning kokanee from egg deposition in the fall to fry emergence the following spring. Okanagan Lake shore-spawning kokanee locations are identified in Figure 4 along with the WSC stations for measuring lake elevations and temperatures.

Figure 4. General location of four quadrants (NW, NE, SW, SE) used in estimating Okanagan Lake kokanee shorespawners (Andrusak et al. 2013).

2.0 Methods

2.1 Distribution and abundance of Sockeye.

The FWMT sockeye sub-model simulates production outcomes for three cohorts of sockeye salmon from the time of spawning in October through egg incubation, emergence, and rearing to the end of the following November. During this interval, the sockeye sub-model supports simulations on daily to weekly time steps are required to reflect mortality processes known to control Okanagan sockeye production variations. Key mortality events during spawning and incubation are flood-and-scour or drought-and-desiccation in the Okanagan River. Adult spawner abundance, sex ratio, timing of egg deposition, and age-specific fecundity are required to initialize sub-model brood year simulations. Daily water temperature values are used in the sockeye sub-model to determine the elapsed time from egg-deposition to egg-hatch and fry emergence.

2.1.1 Sockeye abundance estimates

Annual escapement estimates determined from visual counts on the terminal spawning grounds provide a relative index of abundance of sockeye but are consistently lower compared to Wells Dam ladder counts. This bias reflects the combined effects of the difference between methods employed, viewing environment, and any mortality that occurs between Wells and the spawning grounds (Stockwell and Hyatt 2003). The ONA Fisheries Department conduct float and stream walk surveys of the Index, Channel, and Skaha sections of the Okanagan River spawning grounds (Figure 3 & Table 3). Data is processed in an area-under-the-curve (AUC) estimate, which is the preferred annual escapement value for the FWMT sockeye sub-model. The AUC estimate is calculated using the standard trapezoidal approximation method outlined in Hillborn et al. 1999 (details outlined in Hyatt et al. 2011, 2010). Over the operations of the FWMT years, spawning ground surveys have maintained consistent standards (e.g. design, methods, effort; Stockwell and Hyatt 2003). During this period, peak-live-plus-dead (PLD) estimates have been on average, approximately 29.0% of Wells counts while AUC estimates represent 48% of Wells.

Table 3. Sockeye spawner enumeration method

Sampling session	Sockeye enumeration is conducted from the end of September to beginning of November. A minimum of 7 and up to 11 float and stream-walk surveys of the Index, Channel, and Skaha sections of the Okanagan River spawning grounds are completed. Surveys are conducted on a weekly basis; during the onset of spawner migration to the spawning grounds (end of September), and then increased to intervals of 3 days during the spawning period throughout October-November.
Crews	Depending on the run size, a 3 – 4 person crew enumerates the main channel of the Index section from a boat, with 2 tally counters attached to the paddle and at least 2 tally counters attached to their lifejacket. 2 observers count sockeye holding and spawning on opposite sides of the middle of the channel and 1-2 observers at the front of the boat count sockeye dead and other (Chinook, kokanee, rainbow trout).
Sample area	See Figure 3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Walk) river bank from McIntyre Dam to Deer park. • (Float) Deer park to VDS12/Oliver bridge (break down by reach, including ORRI). Additionally, side channels throughout this reach are walked and all fish counted. • (Drive/walk) VDS 11-1. • (Walk) Skaha outlet to VSD 17. • (Drive/walk) counts of VDS 17-14.
Key data collection	All counts sockeye spawners by live (holding and spawning) and dead. The Channel section counts are conducted by one observer viewing, from each of the Vertical Drop Structures (VDS), upstream to approximately 30-50m. Skaha section counts (Skaha Dam down to VDS 14) are conducted by 1-2 observers viewing from the VDS and path/road.
Additional data	Count kokanee and chinook by live and dead (all other fish species in the drive/walk counts at VDS)
Data analysis	AUC is calculated using the number of live fish observed in each survey and the average residency time of spawning sockeye. In general, the formula is: $AUC = \frac{\sum(x_i + x_{i-1})/2 * (t_i - t_{i-1})}{11}$, where x_i is the number of observed live fish, and t_i is the day of the year.
Field sheets	Appendix A – (Photos - Appendix H)
Data flow	OIB/ONA crews collect field data to send to DFO and ONA leads

2.1.2 Sockeye peak spawning dates

The date of peak spawning is commonly associated with the date on which peak abundance is observed (Cousens et al. 1982). However, peak abundance alone does not always provide sufficient information to confirm the time of peak spawn and subsequent egg deposition. Behavioural observations (e.g. holding, pairing, spawning) of adult salmon can provide a more accurate estimate of the true peak spawn date. Figure 7 illustrates the transition from pre-spawn pair-off and holding behaviour to active spawning as the season progresses.

For FWMT, multiple methods are considered each year to establish a single date for peak spawn (peak egg deposition) for Okanagan sockeye. Understandably, peak spawning would occur over an interval of a number of days; however, for FWMT purposes we need to assign one specific date on which to initiate the sockeye sub-model. Once this date is entered, FWMT allocates a temporal distribution of egg deposition to three weekly cohorts, such that 40% of spawning occurs during the designated peak spawn week and 30% each in the weeks immediately before and after the peak week (Alexander et al. 2008).

Additional “rules” can be applied to establish the peak spawn date for sockeye in the Okanagan River. For example, peak spawn is frequently associated with dates when carcass abundance makes up between approximately 3% and 10% of the total (live plus dead) fish observed on the spawning grounds (Hyatt and Rankin 1999). The peak spawn date may also be identified through the “water temperature rule”, which is defined as the date on which declining, seasonal water temperatures in Okanagan River reach 12°C (Hyatt et al. 2013). This is the historical, average temperature that peak spawning activity typically occurs.

2.2 Biological Traits of Adult Sockeye

ONA field crews conduct a series of dead pitch surveys (pre, peak, and post die-off) throughout three reaches of the Okanagan River: the natural section (from Transect 2 to Hwy 97 Bridge;), the semi-natural section (Hwy 97 Bridge to VDS13; Fig. 3; Table 4). All sockeye carcasses are sampled for length/sex ratio with otoliths removed from a sub-set of these carcasses. The documented “rule of thumb” is to (aim to) biosample (sex, length, otoliths) 5% of the total through Wells. When returns are low, all fish are biosampled if possible, the target is 300-500 fish. The FWMT sockeye sub-model will generate the total number of eggs deposited in this brood year based on the total number of females per age class (below) and age specific fecundity (pre-set in the model).

Table 4. Sockeye spawner biosampling method

Sampling session	Pre, peak and post die-off, determined by enumeration surveys.
Crews	3 walkers, 2 biosamplers
Sample area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Below transect 2 (reach 5) to Broodstock site (reach 8)
Key data collection	Length, sex, otoliths (for aging), thermal marks
Additional data	Scanned for tags
Data analysis	Analysis for sex composition and age at length.
Field sheets	Appendix A – (Photos - Appendix H)
Data flow	OIB/ONA crews collect field data to send to DFO and ONA leads

2.2.1 Deadpitch procedures:

Dead pitch surveys (pre, peak, and post die-off) in the Okanagan River:

- The natural section (from Transect 2 to Hwy 97 Bridge),
- The semi-natural section (Hwy 97 Bridge to VDS13). For FWMT it is not necessary to sample above McIntyre.

Survey dates will be determined from enumeration surveys (enumeration crew lead to be in contact with deadpitch lead). Initial plan is to go out “around” Oct 14/15 (unless crew is seeing a lot of dead fish earlier), then Oct. 20/21 (5 or 6 days later), and then a week after that. This should catch representational sections of the run. Each survey takes approximately 2 – 5 days, depending on returns with a crew minimum of 3 to ‘pitch’ and 2 to biosample.

The goal is to pitch all sockeye carcasses that are within reach regardless of condition. During each survey the following information is recorded:

- Tags,
- All fish are to be cut in half in order to identify counted/sampled fish and thus prevent re-counting on subsequent surveys,
- Record sex of all pitched fish, and
- Record by reach as per other years (Transect 2 to Hwy 97, Hwy 97 to boat launch, boat launch to Island Rd, and Island Rd to broodstock site).

2.2.2 Biosampling procedures

Biosample, target is every 4th or 5th fish pitched which will be determined by the biosample lead. If high numbers of fish return to the spawning grounds, the goal is to take every 5th, or will meet the target before the end of the run. All fish are taken if the run has low numbers.

Data recorded for biosampling (separated by date and reach):

- Length measurements (FL, POH),
- Otoliths removed from every 4th or 5th fish; 250 otoliths for PBS lab not images, and
- Once biosampled, fish are cut in half and thrown back into river.

Target number of otoliths for aging are 300-500. The documented “rule of thumb” is to biosample (sex, length, otoliths) 5% of the total through Wells. Of all the otoliths sampled, age 300-500 are to be weighted - across reach and time. Of the fish to be aged, half are sent to PBS for cross calibration. All otoliths collected will be stored in labeled vials and placed in vials holders (preferably ones that can hold 100 vials), which is completed in the field. Any odd occurrences with the otoliths should be recorded in the data sheets. Some examples are of this are:

- Only one otolith in vial,
- One large otolith & one small in same vial, and
- Broken otoliths

Once samples are back at the lab, the following will be completed:

- Check to make sure all samples are accounted for,
- Check to make sure all samples are labeled, and
- If separating samples, complete one at a time & double check that each vial is labeled with the same number (this is for when otoliths need to be split for different labs to age).

Sample data is to be provided to FWMT team in weekly updates.

2.3 Distribution and abundance of beach spawning kokanee

The Okanagan FWMT system includes a kokanee sub-model (Andrusak et al. 2013) that incorporates the impacts of water storage and release decisions (lake elevation) on egg and alevin survival. The sub-model simulates the developmental progress of Okanagan Lake shore-spawning kokanee from egg deposition in the fall through to completion of fry emergence the following spring. Typically, Okanagan Lake water levels are drawn down during late winter and early spring to accommodate increased inflows from spring run-off. However, about 10% of incubating eggs and alevins are at risk of mortality through desiccation by stranding if lake levels drop 20 cm or more below levels that existed during spawning (Andrusak et al. 2005). The sub-model incorporates daily mean water temperatures to estimate time from egg deposition to 100% fry emergence and as such, predicts the window of vulnerability of eggs and alevins to winter drawdown. FWMT automatically imports daily mean water temperatures and daily mean lake levels from WSC Real-Time Station 08MN083 (Okanagan Lake at Kelowna; Figure 5). Date(s) and location(s) of peak spawn are required to initialize sub-model simulations for the fish-and-water management cycle associated with Okanagan Lake kokanee (Table 5). The kokanee sub-model does not require the input of additional data as it does not take into consideration in-lake survival that is dependent on additional factors unrelated to water management decisions.

Table 5. Kokanee beach spawning methods

Sampling session	Early October to mid November
Crews	1 boat driver, 2 observers
Sample area	Okanagan Lake – three quadrants (SE, NW, NE)
Key data collection	Kokanee spawner enumeration by quadrants by 3 surveys
Additional data	none
Data analysis	The annual spawner escapement estimate is based on the sum of the highest daily count recorded for each of the three quadrants. No expansion factor is applied due to a typically short spawning site residence period
Field sheets	Photos - Appendix C-1
Data flow	FLNRORD & contractor crews collect field data to send ONA leads

2.4 Biological traits of spawning Kokanee

Net 150 moribund kokanee (50 per transect) to determine sex ratios, age class distribution, and age-size relationships of the kokanee spawning population. Otoliths and DNA are retrieved from these samples for lab analysis. Standard sampling methodology was based from Andrusak et al. (2003).

Table 6. Kokanee spawner biosampling methods

Sampling session	Early October to mid November
Crews	1 boat driver, 2 observers
Sample area	Okanagan Lake – three quadrants (SE, NW, NE)
Key data collection	Determine sex ratios, age class distribution, and age-size relationships
Additional data	Otoliths and DNA are retrieved from samples for FLNRORD lab analysis
Data analysis	Length frequency by quadrat is complete.
Field sheets	Appendix C-2
Data flow	FLNRORD & contractor crews collect field data to send ONA leads

2.5 Sockeye egg hatch and fry emergence timing

Sockeye eggs and alevins can be impacted (physical damage and inability to survive in the water column) if redds are scoured as a result of flood control water releases during the pre-emergence incubation period. FWMT coding was updated during the 2008-2009 water-year to incorporate the log-inverse Belehrádek formula (Beacham and Murray 1990) into the sockeye development sub-model. The Belehrádek formula accounts for non-linear effects of variable incubation temperatures on developmental timing and is considered to be a more reliable method to predict hatch and emergence timing for Okanagan sockeye (Hyatt and Stockwell 2010).

Twelve surveys for fry emergence are conducted each spring in March/April, with the goal being to obtain the peak and end of emergence. Sampling occurs once per week until numbers start to increase, then sampling continues every 3 days. After peak is reached, sampling will be conducted approximately 2 times, every 5 days (Table 7).

Table 7. Sockeye fry emergence methods

Sampling session	March/April
Crews	2-3 field crew members/biosamplers
Sample area	VDS 13, Oliver, BC
Key data collection	Developmental stage of fry and number of fry/ hour and velocity of water sieved by the fyke net.
Additional data	Sub-sample of fry length and weight
Data analysis	ONA lead to calculate the total emergence by water volume
Field sheets	Appendix B – (Photos - Appendix H)
Data flow	OIB/ONA crews collect field data to send to DFO and ONA leads

Fyke Net Soak Time: Our ability to interpret seasonal changes in fry emergence both within and between years requires that we maintain relatively constant sampling effort during each trip - that is, one hour of cumulative "soak-time" per trip. The preferred set-up is 4 x 15 minute sets at 21:00, 22:00, 23:00, and 0:00. Over the past several years of sampling, these 4 time sets have produced the majority of fry. If there are problems with debris accumulation, exceptionally high numbers of fish, or flow problems, the following deployment soak times have worked well: sets should be cut back to 7.5 minutes every half hour (8 x 7.5 minute soaks but still 1 hour in total).

Start and Stop Velocity meter readings: Soak times alone will not fully standardize sampling effort if river flow rates change or if nets need to be pulled due to debris accumulation, etc. So it is important the start and stop readings from the velocity-meter in the throat of the sampling gear be recorded so samples can be adjusted to a constant water volume as part of subsequent analysis. Check for recording errors or equipment malfunction. The value for the "stop" reading will always be much higher than the value for the "start" reading.

The number of sockeye fry caught is recorded by developmental stage on the data sheet APPENDIX B. "Note" box is used to indicate dead fry, any eggs observed, fry of other species, etc. If highly experienced crew members are expected to be absent on trips, make certain biosamples are returned to the laboratory and double checked (under good lighting conditions) by personnel who can reliably place sockeye into their appropriate developmental stages as well as identify the difference between sockeye fry and other species. Retain sockeye fry samples for stage length, weight, verification of developmental stage, and possibly species identification (sockeye vs kokanee).

For sampling dates involving catches less than 100 fry, retain all fry captured. For sampling dates involving catches of more than 100 fry, retain 100 captured fry. Additional information required are comments on any equipment malfunctions or environmental conditions that may impact the number of fry collected in the fyke net. (e.g. "when we pulled the net it had folded over during set", high debris conditions, large cottonwood trees floating down river and getting caught on gear, etc.).

2.6 Fry survival and annual smolt production from Osoyoos Lake

Detailed growth, survival and reproduction data for sockeye and kokanee in Osoyoos Lake is collected on an annual basis throughout the year. These performance measures can then be compared with historical and accumulated data to evaluate long-term production trends. Additional data collected is periodic density-size-biomass, egg count, and survival data for all major zooplankton and zooplankton consuming fish species found in Osoyoos Lake (Lawrence, et al. 2009; Table 8).

Table 8. Osoyoos in-lake methods

Sampling session	February – November (Detailed schedule Appendix D)
Crews	2 crew members
Sample area	Osoyoos Lake
Key data collection	Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen, Secchi, Zooplankton, Mysid, ATS
Additional data	As requested by the FWMT steering committee
Data analysis	ATS data is processed by ONA technicians and compared to abundance hauls; zooplankton and mysid data is processed for biomass; temp and DO profiles are created for each survey date
Field sheets	Appendix D-1 – (Photos - Appendix H)
Data flow	ONA crews collect field data to send to DFO and ONA leads

2.6.1 Temperature / Dissolved Oxygen

Calibrate the YSI 650 with the 600OMS sonde each time prior to sampling for each lake. Dissolved oxygen and temperature is measured at the surface (1m) and measured every 1m until 24 m depth, then every 4m until maximum depth. The readings should be recorded on the field data sheet (Appendix D-2), with DO in mg/L and temperature in Celsius.

2.6.2 Secchi Depth (day time only)

To obtain secchi depth use the view tube (polarized sunglasses are not to be worn). If possible have the same person taking the measurements as it is dependent on individual vision. To measure the secchi depth slowly lower the secchi disk from the shady side of the boat until just out of view and make note of the measurement (A), then slowly raise the disk until it is just visible and make note of the measurement (B). The measurement is recorded where the measuring tape hits the surface of the water. $(A+B) / 2 = \text{secchi depth}$. These measurements are recorded on temp/DO field data sheet.

2.6.3 *Mysis relicta* and zooplankton

The Rigosha meters are calibrated twice each year and completed on a calm day. Find a spot in the lake that is at least 35m deep. Record the initial reading of the Rigosha and then lower the calibration ring with Rigosha attached to 30m. Pull up the ring at least 1m / sec, therefore taking 30 seconds to pull up the ring. Be careful not spin the Rigosha when breaking the surface of the water as this adds revolutions to the final Rigosha number. Record the final Rigosha reading and note difference (final – initial = difference). Repeat the above steps to obtain 10 readings per Rigosha, and take the average of these for final calibration number.

The following field methods are used for mysid and zooplankton sampling on both Skaha and Osoyoos lakes with a total of 15 samples per lake Table 5. *Mysis relicta* are collected with a 300 µm mysid net and zooplankton are collected with a 100 µm SCOR (Scientific Committee on Ocean research) vertical haul net (0.25 m² mouth opening). If wind is predicted to be 20 km/hr or higher then reschedule. If weather looks fine start sampling 1 hour after sunset.

Table 9. *Mysis relicta* and zooplankton sample sites for Osoyoos and Skaha Lake.

Sample	Osoyoos Lake Sites sampled	Skaha Lake Sites sampled
<i>Mysis relicta</i>	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
Zooplankton	2, 4, 5, 7, 10	2, 4, 6, 8, 11

At each site (Appendix E-1). the haul distance is 30 m (measured from metal ring of net). Ensure that the depth of the water is reading at least 35m on the depth sounder. Record the Rigosha number being used for the zooplankton net and for the mysid net on the mysid/zoo field form (Appendix E-2). Before each haul record the “start” Rigosha reading and put on 10lb weight. Haul speed should be about 1 m per second. Therefore, it will take 30 seconds to haul the net. When hauling the net, be sure not to let the Rigosha meter spin in the air as the net breaks the surface of the water as this adds extra counts. Read the Rigosha meter and record “end” Rigosha reading. Subtract the start and end Rigosha reading. If the net was 100 % efficient, the difference would be about 300 revolutions (the Rigosha meters spin at about 10 revolutions per m). The reading should be between 50 and 330.

Troubleshooting: *A low reading means that there is a lot of algae in the water clogging the net. A high reading means that you could have either over-spun the meter a bit at the surface, or the boat was drifting and the net was being pulled along horizontally and essentially over fishing. If a high reading is being recorded consistently then the Rigosha may need to be recalibrated. If your meter reading is outside the general range (50-330), then suspect that something is wrong. If you suspect that something is wrong, complete the sample and then take a second sample.*

Rinse the bottom (end) of the net by dipping in and out of the water to make sure all of the sample flushes into the cod end. Wash samples out of the cod end into the 4oz bottles (Mysis) and 250ml jars (Zooplankton) using a three rinse method. Use a wash bottle filled with as the soda water contains CO₂ which puts the mysids and zooplankton to sleep so they don't lose their eggs. Make sure the soda water and sample do not fill over half the bottle as formalin has to be added in a 1:1 ratio. Double the sample volume using 10 % neutral buffered formalin, this is to be added right away in the boat. It is easiest to keep the 10 % formalin mixture in recycled detergent bottles with push down sealing lids. Complete the label (Appendix E-2) in pencil and insert into the bottle with writing facing out.

After sampling has been completed, equipment has to be cleaned and checked for rips or holes each time. The nets will need to be rinsed with a hose (when weather permits). If the nets are dirty wash with a bit of dish soap and rinse well. Make sure that no mysids or zooplankton are stuck to sides. Check nets and cod ends for holes and tears, if any present fix right away using aqua seal/nail polish/marine goop. Hang the nets up in dry place to dry until required for next sampling. If ropes used, hang to dry. Prepare and store all equipment and chemicals ready for the next sampling period. The zooplankton samples along with the combining sheets are sent to Zotec Services to be counted. The mysis samples are processed by the ONA lab.

2.6.4 Acoustic surveys

Acoustic surveys will be used to estimate sockeye and kokanee densities and conducted one hour after sunset. A Biosonics Model DT-X split-beam echosounder with a frequency of 200 KHz is used for collecting acoustic data. In addition, split-beam technology will produce size frequency plots which will help to distinguish between 0+ sockeye and older larger kokanee.

Skaha and Osoyoos Lake are surveyed with 15 transects and 14 transects (Appendix F-1) respectively. Calibration for target strength (Threshold Level) will be followed as in the Biosonics manual (2003). The boat speed will be <5km/hour and GPS plotting to record boat speed and track distance. Check the computer date and time for accuracy and the GPS will be hooked up to the sounder. All data collected will be recorded on the acoustic field form (Appendix F-2).

2.6.5 Trawl surveys

Trawl surveys collect biosamples which will be used to separate sockeye and kokanee and to collect data for fish age, length, weight, and stomach content. A trawl net with a 3m x 7m mouth opening and 18 m long will be used for all collections. Net design is described in Enzenhofer and Hume (1989). This large net will facilitate the collection of 0+ sockeye and larger kokanee.

Trawls will be conducted at night and done from the same boat after the acoustic surveys. The goal is to catch ~300 0+ and 50-100 older age fish per night, number of trawls per sampling session will vary dependent on catch. The catch should include juvenile sockeye and various age classes of kokanee. The idea is to collect the 0+ fish in the strata they are seen then to do deeper trawls (i.e. 30m) to collect older age classes of kokanee as it is suspected that they are deeper in the water column. If a total of 300+ juvenile fish has been reached, then move on to the large fish trawls. The maximum amount of juvenile nerkids to be collected is 400 whether or not you have reached the goal of 50 older age class kokanee. Record catch, by strata and category (e.g. 0+ kokanee, 0+ sockeye, 1+ kokanee etc.). Each trawl set should be assigned a code number and records kept to identify each trawl set with respect to Lake, date, depth, location (Appendix G).

NOTE: *Fish from each trawl set should be placed in Ziploc bags properly labeled. The Ziploc bags then need to be preserved on ice in a cooler and brought to the laboratory for biosampling the following day.*

2.6.6 Fish biological sampling from Osoyoos lake

Once the fish arrive at the laboratory, the fish are then separated into 2 groups (<10cm (0+) and >10cm (1+ and older)).

The fish that are less than 10cm are processed as follows: *all data collected to be recorded on the laboratory data sheet.*

1. If less than 200 fish, all are to be processed. If there are more than 200 fish, use a scoop to randomly remove groups of fish and sample every fish in the scoop. Sample up to 200 fish.
2. Provide all fish with a unique ONA fish number, weigh and measure (FL)

The fish that are larger than 10cm are to be processed as follows: *all data collected to be recorded on the laboratory data sheet*

1. All fish are to be processed.
2. Provide all fish with a unique ONA fish number, weigh and measure (FL)
3. Remove scales and store in scale book. Do not turn over the scales once removed, place into scale book the same way removed.
4. Remove stomach and empty into a container containing 1-part stomach contents and 3 parts 95% ethanol.
5. Place fish bodies into labeled Ziploc bag and freeze. Fish are kept for a year then disposed of.

3.0 References

- Alexander, C.A.D., B. Symonds and K. D. Hyatt [Eds]. 2008. The Okanagan Fish/Water Management Tool: Guidelines for Apprentice Water Managers (v.2.1.000). Prepared for the Canadian Okanagan Basin Technical Working Group (COBTWG) and Douglas County Public Utility District (DCPUD), Draft report submitted to COBTWG and DCPUD, June 2008.
- Andrusak, H., S. Matthews I. McGregor, K. Ashley, G. Wilson, L. Vidmanic, J. Stockner, D. Sebastian, G. Scholten, P. Woodruff, D. Cassidy, J. Webster, A. Wilson, M. Gaboury, P. Slaney, G. Lawrence, W.K. Oldham, B. Janz and J. Mitchell. 2003. Okanagan Lake Action Plan Year 7 (2002) Report. Fisheries Project Report No. RD 106. 2003. Fisheries Management Branch, Ministry of Water, Land and Air Protection, Province of British Columbia.
- Andrusak, H., S. Matthews I. McGregor, K. Ashley, R. Rae, A. Wilson, J. Webster, G. Andrusak, L. Vidmanic, J. Stockner, D. Sebastian, G. Scholten, P. Woodruff, B. Jantz, D. Bennett, H. Wright R. Withler and S. Harris. 2005. Okanagan Lake Action Plan Year 9 (2004) Report. Fisheries Project Report No. RD 111. 2005. Fisheries Management Branch, Ministry of Environment, Province of British Columbia.
- Andrusak, H., A. Wilson, and S. Matthews. 2013. The kokanee sub-model of the Okanagan Fish/Water Management (OKFWM) Tool. Chapter 5 In C. A. D. Alexander, B. Symonds and K. D. Hyatt (Eds) 2013. The Okanagan Fish/Water Management Tool: Guidelines for Apprentice Water Managers (v.2.4.000). Prepared for the Canadian Okanagan Basin Technical Working Group (COBTWG) and Douglas County Public Utility District (DCPUD).
- Beacham, T. D. and C. B. Murray. 1990. Temperature, egg size, and development of embryos and alevins of five species of Pacific salmon: a comparative analysis. *Trans. Am. Fish. Soc.* 119(6): 927-945.
- Hyatt, K. D. and M. M. Stockwell. 2003. Analysis of seasonal thermal regimes of selected aquatic habitats for salmonids populations of interest to the Okanagan Fish and Water Management Tools (FWMT) project. *Can. Manuscr. Rep. Fish. Aquat. Sci.* 2618: viii + 26 p.
- Hyatt, K. D. and D. Machin. 2005. Okanagan Fish and Water Management Tool (FWMT): Operational Deployment and Assessment of the FWMT System to Support 2005-06 Fish-and-Water Management Decisions: Year 1 of 8. Proposal (Sept. 2005) submitted to Douglas County Public Utility District No. 1, Wenatchee Washington. Canadian Okanagan Basin Technical Working Group Secretariat. 34 p.
- Hyatt, K. D., E. Fast, M. Flynn, D. Machin, S. Matthews and B. Symonds. 2001. Water management tools to increase production of Okanagan Sockeye salmon. Fish-Water Management Proposal (June 21, 2001) submitted to Douglas County Public Utility District No. 1, Wenatchee Washington. Canadian Okanagan Basin Working Group Secretariat. 24 p.

- Hyatt, K. D., C. Peters, C. Alexander, and P. Rankin. 2013. The Sockeye sub-model of the Okanagan Fish Water Management (OKFWM) Tool: Chapter 6 In C. A. D. Alexander, B. Symonds and K. D. Hyatt (Eds) 2013. The Okanagan Fish/Water Management Tool: Guidelines for Apprentice Water Managers (v.2.4.000). Prepared for the Canadian Okanagan Basin Technical Working Group (COBTWG) and Douglas County Public Utility District (DCPUD).
- Hyatt, K. D. and M. M. Stockwell. 2010. Fish and Water Management Tool Project Assessments: Record of Management Strategy and Decisions for the 2006-2007 Water Year. Can. Manuscr. Rep. Fish. Aquat. Sci. 2913: ix + 65p.
- Hyatt, K, M. Stockwell, H. Wright, L. Wiens and P. Askey. 2011. Okanagan Fish and Water Management Tools Project Assessments: Brood Year 2010 Salmon (*Oncorhynchus nerka*) Abundance and Biological Traits. Report to file: JSIDS- SRe 01-12. Salmon in Regional Ecosystems Program, Fisheries and Oceans Canada, Nanaimo, B.C. V9T 6N7. 29 p.
- Hyatt, K. D., C. A. D. Alexander, M. M. Stockwell. 2015. A decision support system for improving “fish friendly” flow compliance in the regulated Okanagan Lake and River System of British Columbia. Canadian Water Resources Journal 40(1): 87-110.
- Hyatt, Kim, Margot Stockwell, Howie Wright, Lynnea Wiens and Paul Askey. 2017. Okanagan Fish and Water Management Tools Project Assessments: Brood Year 2012 Sockeye Salmon (*Oncorhynchus nerka*) Abundance and Biological Traits. Report to file: JSIDS- SRe01-17. Salmon in Regional Ecosystems Program, Fisheries and Oceans Canada, Nanaimo, B.C. V9T 6N7. 29 p.
- Hyatt, K. D. Machin, M. Stockwell, T. White, S. Reimer, K. Alex. 2019. Okanagan Fish and Water Management Tools (FWMT) year 2018-2019. Prepared for the FWMT Steering Committee and Douglas County PUD. Prepared by Okanagan Nation Alliance Fisheries Department, Westbank, BC.
- Lawrence, S., H. Wright, C. Mathieu, K. Hyatt, D. McQueen, D. P. Rankin. 2009. Summary of biomonitoring sampling protocol for water chemistry, phytoplankton, zooplankton, mysid shrimp, whitefish and juvenile fish for 2008 Broodyear.
- Stockwell, M. M. and K. D. Hyatt. 2003. A summary of Okanagan Sockeye salmon (*Oncorhynchus nerka*) escapement survey observations by date and river segment from 1947 to 2001. Can. Data. Rep. Fish. Aquat. Sci. 1106: 34 p + CD-ROM.

Appendix A: Sockeye enumeration field data sheet

ONAFD
2019 Fall Data Sheet

Sockeye Enumeration

Date:

SNA
Okanagan Nation Alliance

ABOVE MCINTYRE DAM												
Crew Initials:	Water Clarity:			To Bottom			OR			Depth(m):		
	Full	Bright	Medium	Dark	<input type="checkbox"/> L	<input type="checkbox"/> L-M	<input type="checkbox"/> L-M	<input type="checkbox"/> M	<input type="checkbox"/> M	<input type="checkbox"/> M-H	<input type="checkbox"/> H	
Precipitation:	% Cloud cover:			If less than H, why?								
Wind:	<input type="checkbox"/> Light breeze	<input type="checkbox"/> Medium	<input type="checkbox"/> Strong wind									
Comments:												
REACH	Time	Holding	Spawning	Dead	Quality	Live KO	Dead KO	Live CH	Dead CH			
Skaha Dam to	S:											
VDS 17	E:											
VDS 16	S:											
	E:											
VDS 15	S:											
	E:											
VDS 14	S:											
	E:											
TOTAL:												

Sockeye Enumeration

ONAFD
2019 Fall Data Sheet

Date: _____

INDEX SECTION												
Crew Initials:	Water Clarity: To Bottom OR Depth(m):											
Sky Brightness: Full Bright Medium Dark	Stream Visibility: <input type="checkbox"/> L <input type="checkbox"/> L-M <input type="checkbox"/> M			<input type="checkbox"/> M-H <input type="checkbox"/> H								
Precipitation:	% Cloud cover: <input type="checkbox"/> Light breeze <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Strong wind			Count Quality: <input type="checkbox"/> L <input type="checkbox"/> L-M <input type="checkbox"/> M			<input type="checkbox"/> M-H <input type="checkbox"/> H					
Wind: <input type="checkbox"/> Light breeze <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Strong wind	If less than H, why? Comments:											
Air Temp:												
REACH	Time	Holding	Spawning	Dead	Quality	Live KO	Dead KO	Live CH	Dead CH			
1a: McIntyre Dam to Deer Park	S: E:											
1b: Deer Park to Hwy 97 Bridge Crossing	S: E:											
2a: Hwy 97 Bridge to Semi-Natural Section	S: E:											
2b: Semi-natural section to Park Rill	S: E:											
2c: Park Rill to ORRI (Cross Sec. 8)	S: E:											
2d: ORRI (Cross Sec. 8) to VDS13	S: E:											
3: VDS13 to Oliver Bridge Crossing	S: E:											
TOTAL:												

Sockeye Enumeration

ONAFD
2019 Fall Data Sheet

Date:

VDS SECTION											
Crew Initials:			Water Clarity:			To Bottom OR			Depth(m):		
Sky Brightness: Full Bright Medium Dark			Stream Visibility: <input type="checkbox"/> L <input type="checkbox"/> L-M <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> M-H <input type="checkbox"/> H								
Precipitation:			% Cloud cover:			Count Quality: <input type="checkbox"/> L <input type="checkbox"/> L-M <input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> M-H <input type="checkbox"/> H					
Wind: <input type="checkbox"/> Light breeze <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Strong wind			If less than H, why?								
Comments:											
REACH	Time	Holding	Spawning	Dead	Quality	Live KO	Dead KO	Live CH	Dead CH		
VDS 11	S: E:										
VDS 10	S: E:										
VDS 9	S: E:										
VDS 8	S: E:										
VDS 7	S: E:										
VDS 6	S: E:										
VDS 5	S: E:										
VDS 4	S: E:										
VDS 3	S: E:										
VDS 2	S: E:										
VDS 1	S: E:										
										TOTAL:	

Appendix B: Sockeye fry emergence field data sheet

OKANAGAN SOCKEYE FRY EMERGENCE SAMPLING DATE _____ 2018

Set #	Set Time	Pull Time	Meter Reading		Total Sockeye Fry	FRY STAGE								
			Start	Stop		1	2	3	4	5				
NOTES:														
NOTES:														
NOTES:														
NOTES:														

FAX TO: Margot Stockwell at 250-756-7138, or
email scanned copy to margot.stockwell@dfo-mpo.gc.ca and dmachin@sylix.org

Appendix C-1: Okanagan Lake Kokanee shore-spawning enumeration

DATE:
WATERBODY:

QUADRANT:
REACH COLLECTED:

Time	Reach	Fish Count	Comments

Appendix D-1: Osoyoos Lake sampling schedule

Week starting each Monday	Oxygen and temperature		Zooplankton	Mysis relicta		Fish density (acoustic)	Fish (trawl)	Moon, illuminated fraction
May	x		x	x				
July	x		x	x				
August						x	x	On new moon
September	x		x	x				
October	x		x	x				
October	x					x	x	On new moon
November	x		x	x				
November	x					x	x	On new moon
Feb/March 2020	x		x	x		x	x	On new moon

Appendix D-2: Temperature, dissolved oxygen, and secchi field data sheet

Lake (circle one)	SKAHA	OSOYOOS	OKANAGAN
Station		Secchi (m)	
Date:	2018	Month	Day
Depth (m)	Temperature	Oxygen (mg/L)	
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			
9			
10			
11			
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			
24			
28			
32			
36			
40			
44			
48			
52			
Comments			

Appendix E-1: Osoyoos Mysid and zooplankton sites.

Appendix E-2: Mysid and zooplankton field data sheet and label data sheet.

Date:					Methods:	Mysid (circle one):	WINCH	MANUAL
Crew:						Mysid Rigosha #:		
Weather:						Zoopl. (circle one):	WINCH	MANUAL
						Zoopl. Rigosha #:		

Lake	DFO Site	Mesh Size	Zoo OR Mys	Rigosha Start	Rigosha End	Rigosha Difference	Depth (m)	Start Time
	1						30	
	1						30	
	2						30	
	2						30	
	3						30	
	3						30	
	4						30	
	4						30	
	5						30	
	5						30	
	6						30	
	6						30	
	7						30	
	7						30	
	8						30	
	8						30	
	9						30	
	9						30	
	10						30	
	10						30	
	11						30	
	11						30	

(circle one):	ZOOPLANKTON	MYSIS										
Lake: (circle one)	SKAHA	OSOYOOS	OKANAGAN									
Date 2019:	Month _____	Day _____	Hour _____									
Station (circle one)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
Depth 30m, zoopl mesh = 100um, mysis mesh=300um												
Rigosha IN:	_____										OUT:	_____
Rigosha DIFFERENCE:	_____											

Appendix F-1: Acoustic transects Osoyoos Lake.

Appendix G: Trawling field data sheet.

TRAWL DATA FIELD FORM (year)						
Administrative & Physical Features Summary						
LAKE			Sheet		of	
DATE			Moon Stage			
CREW			Water Clarity			
START TIME			Surface Water Temp.			
END TIME			Cloud Cover			
			Precipitation			
General light conditions on Surface:						
Predominant bottom type:						
Mean Waterbody Depth:						
Maximum Waterbody Depth:						
TRAWL DATA						
Trawl Code (ddmmyy-haul#)						
Haul Information						
Haul Number						
Start Location	Latitude					
	Longitude					
End Location	Latitude					
	Longitude					
Bearing of tow						
Start Tow Time						
End Tow Time						
Duration of Tow						
Cable Out (m)						
Speed Over Ground (km/hr, rpm)						
Top Bar (m)						
Wind direction						
Est. Wind Speed						
Est. Wind Height (m)						
Catch Summary						
No. 0+ Kokanee/Sockeye						
No. 1+ Kokanee						
No. 2+ Kokanee						
Other						
General Comments:						

Appendix H: Photo Documentation.

SOCKEYE ENUMERATION

SOCKEYE EMERGENCE

ACOUSTICS AND TRAWLING

DEADPITCH (BIOSAMPLING)

KOKANEE SHORESPAWNERS

